

RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDOMETRIAL HYPERPLASTIC PROCESSES IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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In the modern world, hyperplastic processes of the endometrium (HPE) are a pressing problem for women of reproductive age. Hyperplastic processes of the endometrium constitute a large and diverse group, in most cases associated with hormonal disorders, in the form of a compensatory reaction or increased functional requirements, in which the structural elements of tissues cannot satisfy these functions [1]. Despite the indisputable high importance of knowledge of the pathogenetic variability of the development of HPE and the choice of tactics for managing patients, it is no less necessary to clarify the morphological structure of HPE, the pathohistological nature of the surrounding endometrium, and the concomitant pathology of the endo- and myometrium, which indicates the similarity of the pathogenetic development of mechanisms leading to hyperplastic processes in tissues [2]. From the point of view of pathogenesis, HPE is the result of long-term exposure to excess estrogen levels, which, indifference from progesterone level, stimulates the growth of endometrial cells. The prevalence of HPE may vary depending on the age of women and the form of the disease and is, according to [3], from 10-30%. HPE is detected to a greater extent in women aged 45-55 years; in this age group, HPE has a tendency to recur and malignancy. Relapses of HPE serve as an indication for repeated diagnostic curettage or surgical interventions with removal of the uterus. In this regard, the search for and assessment of risk factors for the development of endometrial hyperplasia in women of reproductive age remains relevant and in demand.

Prospective studies of 93 patients of reproductive age suffering from hyperplastic pathological processes in the absence of malignant neoplasms were conducted at two departments of obstetrics and gynecology № 1 and № 2 of the SEI "Avicenna Tajik State Medical University" at the Republican Maternity Hospitals № 1 and № 2. The control group included 33 women who sought pregnancy planning — pregravid preparation. The main group consisted of 60 women with HPE. The diagnosis of HPE was verified histologically by taking an endometrial biopsy during hysteroscopy. The examination in both groups included a general physical examination, measurement of height and body weight with calculation of the body mass index (BMI), assessment of the somatic health of women.

The clinical history of women in both groups reflected the history of the current disease and its symptoms, such as intermenstrual bleeding, cycle duration, intensity of discharge, presence of clots, as well as menstrual history, use of medications, features of reproductive function, frequency of use of various methods of contraception, data on gynecological and extragenital diseases of women, surgical interventions on the abdominal cavity and pelvic organs, presence of sexually transmitted infections and social and everyday features.

The patients in the main group were of late reproductive age, while in the control group there were more often women of active reproductive age, since the prevalence of HPE increases proportionally to age.

Given the prevalence of obesity and its association with HPE, all patients were assessed for body mass index (BMI). The body mass index in women in the main and control groups ranged from 21, 7 to 29, 4 kg/ m² and from 22,0 to 26,5 kg/ m², respectively (p=0.02). In both examined groups, the age of menarche did not differ - 13.0. No statistically significant differences were found in the duration of the menstrual cycle and the duration of menstrual bleeding between the patients of the

main and control groups. The duration of the menstrual cycle in the main group ranged from 27.0 to 30.0 days and the duration of menstruation from 5.0 to 6.0 days, and in the control group from 27.0 to 30.0 days and from 4.0 to 6.0 days, respectively ($p > 0.05$).

Analysis of clinical and anamnestic data allowed us to identify the following risk factors for the development of HPE in women of reproductive age: age over 35 years, excess body weight, gastrointestinal diseases, irregular menstrual cycle in history, presence of primary infertility, uterine fibroids, HPE, chronic endometritis, medical abortions in history and diagnostic curettage.

Studying risk factors for the development of HPE in women of reproductive age will allow for disease prevention and preservation of patients' reproductive function. Further studies should be aimed at an individual approach to the treatment of patients with HPE, taking into account risk factors for its development and prevention of relapses.

Literature

1. Khushvakhtova, E. Kh. Diagnostic value of various methods of examination of patients of reproductive age with hyperplastic processes of the endo- and myometrium [Text] / E. Kh. Khushvakhtova, M. Kh. Kurbonova, F. M. Akilova // Proceedings of the VII Congress of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. - Dushanbe. - 2022. - P. 289-293.
2. Krasilnikova, A.K. Risk factors for the development of endometrial hyperplasia with abnormal uterine bleeding in women of reproductive age [Text] / D.A. Malyshkina, S.M. Gasanova, T.M. Kamenkova // Russian Bulletin of Obstetrician-Gynecologist.-2023, Vol.23, No.6, P.48-54.
3. Wang Y, Genetic and epigenetic alterations in endometrial hyperplasia and endometrial cancer [Text] /Y. Wang, L. Zhang, J. Wang [et al.] //J Cancer Res Clin Oncol. 2020; 146(12):2911-2922. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00432-020-03487-2>

